

FOOD SAFETY AWARENESS AND PRACTICES OF STREET FOOD VENDORS IN MIDSAYAP

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Food Safety Awareness and Practices of Street Food Vendors in Midsayap

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out how much knowledge there was and how many procedures there were about food safety among Midsayap's street sellers. A descriptive-correlational design was used, with data analysis done using Spearman's Rho and questionnaires. The results showed that although the suppliers needed to practice consistently, they were aware of the issue. Though they were aware of the fundamentals of food safety, their methods differed greatly. To guarantee street food safety in Midsayap, the report advises municipal authorities to give food safety laws priority and to impose more stringent inspections.

Keywords: *street food vendor awareness, street food vendor practices, foodborne illness prevention*

Introduction

The expertise and methods of street food vendors about food safety have been the subject of numerous investigations. While merchants were typically aware of food safety and hygiene, Chopra (2021) pointed out that they lacked the tools and training necessary to put these procedures into reality consistently. Yusuf (2020) emphasized the necessity of ongoing education and reinforcement to enhance street food vendors' adherence to food safety regulations.

Although street foods are well-liked and reasonably priced, their sale by unhygienic and unsafe sellers seriously risks consumers' health (Sezgin, 2016; Nonato, 2016; Verma, 2020). According to Sezgin (2016), these dangers can result in food- and water-borne illnesses, including food poisoning, hepatitis, and diarrhea. Notwithstanding these reservations, street food in underdeveloped nations can supply sufficient protein and energy (Steyn, 2013). Verma (2020) highlights that street food operators continue to face a serious challenge regarding the absence of regulation and appropriate training.

Food safety is a primary social responsibility as food is not just a matter of consumption but life and death. Food handlers, especially street food vendors, are crucial when considering food safety. Their practices affect the people who consume them and all who depend on them for meals. Food safety should be the primary concern of all food handlers. The local government health officials are concerned with the growing number of street food vendors, which is also the main reason for food-borne and waterborne diseases. It is now difficult for them to monitor street food vendors' sanitary practices regarding their hygiene, preparing, handling, serving, and storing foods.

In this light, the researchers conducted this study to evaluate the food safety awareness and practices of those involved in selling foods along the streets of the Municipality of Midsayap.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the food safety awareness and practices of street food vendors in the Municipality of Midsayap. It aimed to answer the following research questions in particular:

1. What are the socio-demographic characteristics of the street food vendors in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. educational attainment;
 - 1.4. the type of business operation; and
 - 1.5. vending location and availability of sanitary permit?
2. What are the levels of awareness of street food vendors on food safety?
3. What is the extent of respondents' food safety practices?
4. Do the street food vendors' levels of awareness significantly relate to their extent of food safety practices?

Literature Review

Food is indispensable to all human beings, as reported by Latham (2007); the food industry plays an important role in the developing countries in meeting the food demands of the urban dwellers. Street foods feed millions of people daily with a wide variety of foods that are relatively cheap and easily accessible.

Winarno, 2012 in his article "The Street Food Sector in Asia and the Pacific" reported on the growth of the street vendors and the growing number of urban poor and the mobilization of women into the work force. Street foods are not only far cheaper than restaurants or fast-food joints, but much more cost-effective than even home prepared food. Many women are participating in the economy, and

this has constrained their ability to prepare elaborate meals for their families at home, this necessitating them to procure street foods as a supplement to other home cooked food. The street food trade provides numerous employment opportunities. Street food vending has been known to generate income a few times above those on the poverty line in many developing countries.

“National Policy on Street Vendors – 2011” of the Ministry of Urban Development of Poverty Alleviation says that Mumbai has the largest number of street vendors and women with the ages of 18-50 years old constitute a large chunk of street vendors. In almost every city, urban vending is not only a source of employment but provides affordable services to the majority of the urban population.

Street vendors selling food are often poor, uneducated and untrained according to Singh et al., 2016 in their article “Impact of Health Education Intervention of Food safety and Hygiene of Street Food Vendors”. They are often ignorant about food hygiene, which are the conditions and measures necessary to ensure the safety of food from production to consumption. Lack of adequate food hygiene can lead to food-borne illnesses due to improper food handling practices, and in extreme events, even death of all customers.

According to De Guzman et al. (2013) in their article "Street Foods in the Philippines: Health, Nutrition, Management and Livelihood Aspects," the nature of the business operation reveals that the street food business's timetable changes depending on where it operates and what kind of food is sold. A few of them were open twenty-four hours a day. Most of them seemed to be immigrants from the provinces.

The public needs sanitary permits to guarantee that the restaurants, bars, and other enterprises they frequent are clean places to manufacture, process, store, and serve food and beverages. Public health is given priority in accordance with Presidential Decree No. 856, the Code of Sanitation, subject to preservation and promotion. The first part of the decree deals with the hygienic permits that street food vendors must obtain. Infectious disease-free status is verified through examinations of the food handlers requesting for sanitary permits. Section 15 of the Presidential Decree stipulates these.

Carillo and Rodriguez (2018) noted in her article "Street Foods in Bangkok - The Nutritional Contribution and the Contaminants Content of Street Foods" that the vending activities were situated close to a school and that crowded places like marketplaces, recreation centers, and transit hubs frequently result in cleanliness issues. Snacks, meals, and drinks are the three primary food categories. The facilities and equipment in the ambulatory category of vendors are typically modest in size. Food was usually served on traditional pottery, aluminum plates and bowls, and wooden bowls. This vendor sold cleaning water in a tiny plastic pail. The vendors include a mobile rig, an insulated ice box, a stove for cooking meals, and a sink for washing. Some of them are having cooking utensils, tables and benches as well as having serving facilities.

Abdussalam, 2006 in his report "Essential Safety Requirements for Street Vended Foods", studied about in the hygienic handling of street vended foods and the attention to containers of pastes, sauces and other food activities, monitoring them for pathogen growth and visible deterioration of water used for drinking and preparation of beverages. Water used for this purpose should be potable water. Water used for washing utensils, food and hands should be safe and should not be reused. Ice to be used in beverages and food should be prepared from potable water and should be transported and stored in a hygienic manner. Foods to be eaten, raw should be prepared with special attention to cleanliness. Preparing and processing of food are to avoid direct and indirect contact between raw and cooked or prepared food which will be consumed without further heating. The vehicle used for transport should be clean and should not carry animals. Prepared food should be kept at a temperature of at least 60°C to prevent microbial growth. Handling of cooked foods should be kept to a minimum to reduce the likelihood of introducing pathogens. Vending units should be designed and constructed so that they are easily cleaned and maintained. Equipment, utensils and other containers should be made of materials which do not release toxin or hazardous chemicals into food and beverages. Raw meat, poultry or fish should be handled carefully; their preparation should be carried out using separate equipment and utensils. Food handlers should be educated to wear clean and proper clothing according to prevailing local standards. Food handlers should wash their hands with soap and water after engaging in any activities that are likely to introduce biological, chemical or physical hazards. Food should be prepared and sold in a clean well-lit place protected from strong sun, dust, rain and wind.

It was discovered by Azanza et al. (2012) in their work "Microbial Hazards of Street Vended Grilled Chicken Intestine" that street vending of grilled chicken is common in the Philippines. The public finds the product enticing due to its cheap cost, however a significant section of the population finds it unsafe. The use of the sauces in an unhygienic manner puts customers' health at danger. Risks related to street vending include: - contamination from pre-cooked touch surfaces, extra contamination from food colors, and contamination from raw chicken intestines.

Azanza et al. (2012) also, in their article, "Microbial Hazards in Street Vended Fish Balls in the Philippines," revealed that fish ball street vendors have already become permanent fixtures in the main commercial streets of the Philippines, particularly in Manila. The study identified some microbial hazards associated with the street vending operations of fish balls and their different sources. They were found to contain detectable levels of coliforms and salmonella. These levels of microbial contaminations in the sources increased over the 6 hours of the vending operation. The hands of fish ball vendors were also shown to contain increasing amounts of microbial contaminants throughout the vending operations.

Mohan et al. (2009) in their article "Surveying Vendors of Street Food," analyze the safety of the Street vendor food. The vendors have good knowledge of food safety and cholera but persist in unsafe practices. Around 87 percent of the vendors used stored water, usually

in wide-mouthed vessels prone to contamination. Public health planning and intervention data can be gathered rapidly with this method of surveying street vendors. Santos et al. (2016), in their article "Caloocan Vending Program: Makati City Clears its Sidewalks," reveal that the Makati city government recognizes that the proliferation of sidewalk vending is a social phenomenon brought about by the problem of massive unemployment and widespread poverty and recognize that they cannot just sit down and do nothing.

To lower the risk of food-borne pathogenic diseases, Mensah et al. (2015) proposed in their article "Safety and Quality Evaluation of Street Foods Sold in Zaria, Nigeria" that street food vendors and the public need to be educated on the significance of environmental sanitation and safe food handling practices. In their 2008 paper, "Food Safety Knowledge and Practices of Street Food Vendors in a Philippines University Campus," Ortega et al. addressed waste management, food legislation, food contamination, good manufacturing practices, and health and personal hygiene. Their investigation revealed that sellers needed awareness of food laws and proper garbage disposal. There was a sizable discrepancy between knowledge and practice, primarily attributable to street food vendors' propensity to compromise food safety for financial reasons.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive-correlational methodology, which investigated the characteristics of a given population, measuring the specified variables of awareness and practices of street food vendors regarding food safety. A descriptive methodology was employed to assess the level of awareness and extent of practices of street food vendors regarding food safety. A correlational methodology was also used to investigate any relationship between these two variables.

Respondents

The study's respondents were the 40 street food vendors of Midsayap North, Cotabato, who are only vending in the town area.

Instrument

The study utilized an accidental sampling method to select its respondents. Accidental sampling is a non-probability method in which the researchers meet by chance and are included in this sample. The researchers chose this method since vendors are working and busy serving customers; thus, choosing them randomly takes much work (Khan, 2020). However, since the researchers used the accidental sampling method, anybody in the town area of Midsayap could be chosen during the survey.

Procedure

After validating and pre-testing, the questionnaire for reliability, a letter was sent to the Municipal Mayor asking permission to conduct the study in his jurisdiction. Upon approval, copies of the questionnaires were personally distributed to the chosen respondents after talking with them. The respondents were able to answer the questionnaire with ample time given to them.

The researchers assured the respondents that their responses would be kept confidential. The questionnaires were then gathered, tabulated, and analyzed using SPSS or the Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

Results and Discussion

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 deals with the description of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, educational attainment, type of business operation, vending location, and the availability of sanitary permit.

Age

In Table 1, the data reveals that most of the respondents' ages are within the range of 16-26 and 49-59 with 22.5% followed by ages of 38-48 with 20%, then ages 27-37 with 17.5%, the ages of 60-70 with 15% and the ages of 71 and above with 2.5%.

Gender

In terms of gender, the table shows that most of the street food vendors are females. There were 27 female respondents with the percentage of 67.5 and 13 male respondents with the percentage of 32.5%

Educational Attainment

In terms of educational attainment of the street food vendors, the table indicates that out of 40 respondents, ten (10) of them or 25% claimed high school level, thirteen (13) of them or 32.5% claimed high school graduate, 8 of them or 20% claimed elementary level and college graduate respectively were both claimed by four (2) of them or 10% and one (1) of them claimed that he is an elementary graduate.

Type of Business Operation

In terms of the type of business operation, six (6) street food vendors or 15% of them stated that they operate their business every

weekend. Nineteen (19) of them or 47.5% are operating on weekdays and fifteen (15) of them or 37.5% are operating for the whole week.

Vending Location

In terms of the street food vendors' vending location, twenty (20) of the respondents or 50% are vending outside the school premises. Seventeen (17) of them or 42.5% are vending near the market areas, two (2) of them or 5% are vending near the transportation terminals and one (1) street food vendor or 2.5% is vending near the plaza.

Availability of Sanitary Permit

In terms of the street food vendors' availability of sanitary permit, eleven (11) of them or 27.5% stated that they don't have sanitary permits and twenty-nine (29) of them or 72.5 stated that they have sanitary permits.

Table 1. *Socio-demographic characteristics of street food vendors in Midsayap, Cotabato*

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age of Respondents		
16-26	9	22.5
27-37	7	17.5
38-48	8	20
49-59	9	22.5
60-70	6	15
71-above	1	2.5
Gender		
Male	13	32.5
Female	27	67.5
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level	4	10.0
Elementary Graduate	1	2.5
High School Level	10	25.0
High School Graduate	13	32.5
College Level	8	20.0
College Graduate	4	10.0
Type of Business Operation		
Weekend	6	15.0
Weekdays	19	47.5
Whole Week	15	37.5
Vending		
Outside the school premises	20	50.0
Market areas	17	42.5
Transportation terminals	2	5.0
Plaza	1	2.5
Availability of Sanitary Permit		
Yes	29	72.5
No	11	27.5
Total	40	100

Street Food Vendors' Level of Awareness on Food Safety

The table 2 presents the street food vendors' level of awareness on food safety. As seen from the results, the street food vendors are very much aware on food safety revealed by the grand mean of 4.58.

Table 2. *Street food vendors' level of awareness of food safety in Midsayap, Cotabato*

Items	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Washing of hands before work reduces the risk of food contamination.	4.88	Very Much Aware
2. Proper cleaning and sanitation of utensils reduces the risk of food contamination.	4.88	Very Much Aware
3. Eating and drinking in the work place increase the risk of food contamination.	4.60	Very Much Aware
4. Wearing masks is an important practice to reduce the risk of food contamination.	4.53	Very Much Aware
5. Raw and cooked foods should be stored separately to reduce the risk of food contamination.	4.80	Very Much Aware

6.	Food handlers who have abrasions or cuts on their hands should not touch food.	4.65	Very Much Aware
7.	Wearing hairnets is an important practice to reduce the risk of food contamination	4.43	Much Aware
8.	Frozen foods must be defrosted before cooking.	4.73	Very Much Aware
9.	During infectious disease of the skin, it is necessary to take a leave from work.	4.68	Very Much Aware
10.	The health status of workers should be evaluated before employment.	4.73	Very Much Aware
11.	Abortion in pregnant women can be induced by food-borne pathogens.	4.03	Much Aware
12.	AIDS can be transmitted by food	3.09	Much Aware
13.	Children, healthy adults, pregnant women, and older individuals are at equal risks for food poisoning.	4.43	Much Aware
14.	Vending stall must be maintained in a clean condition.	4.85	Very Much Aware
15.	There must be adequate waste disposal facilities available.	4.83	Very Much Aware
Grand Mean		4.58	Very Much Aware
Standard Deviation		0.82	

As shown in the table, street food vendors' level of awareness on food safety, most of the respondents are very much aware on item number one (1) and two (2) which states that (1) washing of hands before work and (2) proper cleaning and sanitation of utensils reduces the risk of food contamination which have weighted means of 4.88 respectively, followed by item number fourteen (14) which states that vending stall must be maintained in a clean condition have a weighted mean of 4.85, then item number fifteen (15) which states that there must be adequate waste disposal facilities available with a weighted mean of 4.83 with a description of very much aware.

Item number eleven (11) and twelve (12) obtained the lowest mean result. Item number eleven (11) which states that abortion in pregnant women can be induced by food-borne pathogens has a weighted mean of 4.03, and item number twelve (12) which states that AIDS can be transmitted by food have a weighted mean of 3.90 with a description of much aware.

Moreover, the grand mean of street food vendors' level of awareness of 4.58 and standard deviation of 0.82 which has a description of "Very Much Aware".

Street Food Vendors' Extent of Practices on Food Safety

The table 3 presents the street food vendors' extent of practices on food safety. As seen from the results, the street food vendors always practice food safety revealed by the grand mean of 4.65.

Table 3. *The street food vendors' extent of practices on food safety in Midsayap, Cotabato*

Items	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Washing hands in clean water each time before handling, preparing and serving food.	4.90	Always Practiced
2. Reporting to work in good health, and dressed in clean attire.	4.80	Always Practiced
3. Potable (safe) water is used for contact with food, food contact surfaces, and ice.	4.98	Always Practiced
4. All food containers have tight fitting cover and are free from dust.	4.80	Always Practiced
5. Using clean utensils.	4.93	Always Practiced
6. Wearing hairnets, gloves, masks, and aprons in preparing the products.	2.68	Sometimes Practiced
7. Checking if the food is fresh, edible, and free from larva.	4.98	Always Practiced
8. Keeping fingernails clean.	4.35	Often Practiced
9. Single eating articles (like plastics, straws, plastic cups, and etc.) are thrown away after use.	4.88	Always Practiced
10. Treating and bandaging wounds and sores immediately.	4.88	Always Practiced
11. Provide spoons or tongs so hands	4.85	Always Practiced

do not touch food directly.		
12. Maintaining the cleanliness of grilled pan/ frying pan and making sure it's not greasy and free from stain.	4.58	Always Practiced
13. Areas are generally clean and orderly, free from odor.	4.63	Always Practiced
14. Separates the raw foods from ready-to-eat foods to prevent food contamination.	4.98	Always Practiced
15. Does not smoke during the handling or preparation of food.	4.58	Always Practiced
Grand Mean	4.65	Always Practiced
Standard Deviation	0.62	

Items number three (3), seven (7), and fourteen (14) which state (3) Potable water is used for contact with food, food contact surfaces, and ice, (7) Checking if the food is fresh, edible, and free from larva and (14) Separates the raw foods from ready-to-eat foods to prevent food contamination obtained the highest mean of 4.98 and a rank of Always Practiced respectively, followed by, item number five (5) Using clean utensils has a weighted mean of 4.93, then item number one (1) Washing of hands in clean water each time before handling, preparing and serving food with a weighted mean of 4.90.

Items nine (9) and ten (10), (9) Single-eating articles are thrown away after use and (10) Treating and bandaging wounds and sores immediately obtained a weighted mean of 4.88 respectively. Item number eleven (11), Provide spoons or tongs so hands do not touch food directly have a weighted mean of 4.85, followed by the items number two (2) and four (4), (2) Reporting to work in good health, and dressed in clean attire and (4) All food containers have tight fitting cover and are free from dust obtained a weighted mean of 4.80 respectively, item number thirteen (13) Areas are generally clean and orderly, free from odor have a weighted mean of 4.63, then items number twelve (12) and fifteen (15), (12) Maintaining the cleanliness of grilled pan/frying pan and making sure it's not greasy and free from stain and (15) Does not smoke during the handling or preparation of food obtaining 4.58 weighted mean. Item number eight (8) was described as often practiced of the street food vendors with a weighted mean of 4.35. While item number six (6) obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.68 and revealed as Sometimes Practiced of the street food vendors on food safety.

The Relationship between the Street Food Vendors' Levels of Awareness and the Extent of Practices on Food Safety

Table 4 presents the relationship between the street food vendors' level of awareness and extent of practices on food safety using the Spearman Rho correlation.

Table 4. *The Relationship between the Street Food Vendors' Levels of Awareness and Extent of Food Safety Practices using Spearman's Rho*

Variables	N	Coefficient of Correlant	Pvalue	Decision
Level of Awareness on Food Safety	40	1.00		
Extent of Food Safety Practices on	40	-.040	.804	Not Significant
N= Not Significant at .05 level (2-tailed)				
Normality Test:				
		Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	(P-value= .002)	Normality assumption is not met
		Shapiro-Wilk Test	(P-value= .000)	Normality assumption is not met

The table 4 presents the relationship between the levels of awareness and the extent of practices of street food vendors on food safety. Using the Spearman's rho, fitting statistical tool for distribution found out that normality is not met using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test with the P-value of .002 and Shapiro-Wilk Test with the P-value of .000. It was stated that if the P-value is lesser than or equal to .05 the normality assumption is not met. Higher than .05 the distribution is normal.

The variables measured are level of awareness on food safety with n=40, the coefficient of correlation for the level of awareness is 1.00 and the extent of food safety practices is -.040 with the P-value of .804 greater than .05. Therefore, it is found that there is no significant relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of practices of the street food vendors on food safety. Thus, the null hypothesis which states the there is no significant relationship in the level of awareness and the extent of practices of the street food vendors on food safety is accepted.

Conclusions

Based on the research conducted and the respondents' responses, we conclude that most street food vendors were between the range of 16-26 and 49-59 years old. Most of the street food vendors were female and were high school graduates. They had their business operation during weekdays and were vending outside the school premises. The majority of the street food vendors also have sanitary permits.

The data on the street food vendors' awareness level shows they are very aware of food safety measures. On the other hand, the street food vendors' extent of practices on food safety also describes what is always practiced. We concluded that the street food vendors were highly aware and always practiced food safety in preparing, handling, and serving food.

It is also found that the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of practices of the street food vendors on food safety, is accepted. This implies that despite street food vendors' knowledge or level of awareness regarding food safety, their practices are different. They need to follow what they know about food safety.

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